

IMPACT OF STUDENT SUPPORT SYSTEM AND PARENTAL QUALIFICATION ON COGNITIVE DISSONANCE AMONG IXTH GRADE ADOLESCENT LEARNERS

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Abstract

Cognitive Dissonance refers to the psychological inconsistency that people who hold two or more cognitions, and experiences i.e., it is a state of psychological discomfort called cognitive dissonance (Festinger, 1957). Cognitive dissonance started emerging from the age of 2 (Wiesmann et al., 2022) and existed till old age (Cooper and Feldman, 2019). However, adolescence became a critical phase to study cognitive dissonance as this stage undergoes a lot of changes such as psychological and physical changes.

AIM OF THE STUDY: The present study aims to understand and find the relationship between the student support system and cognitive dissonance and on the other the study aims to understand the impact between parent qualification and cognitive dissonance.

SAMPLE: A sample of 200 students has been taken from 10 private schools in the Amritsar district by using a simple random technique.

METHOD: A descriptive study using a survey as a technique was conducted.

STATISTICAL MEASURES USED: Mean, Coefficient of correlation, and Percentage analysis were adopted as a statistical technique.

CONCLUSION: The study revealed that the student support system has a negative correlation with the cognitive dissonance of IX-grade learners of P.S.E.B schools, which that means, with the proper student support system, cognitive dissonance can be reduced. The study indicated that boys from these schools have higher cognitive dissonance scores than girls. And also concluded that parental qualification has an impact on cognitive dissonance.

Keywords: *Cognitive Dissonance, Student Support System, Parent Qualification.*

INTRODUCTION

The psychological discrepancy that people who possess two or more cognitions experience is known as cognitive dissonance; it is a state of psychological discomfort (Festinger, 1957). Even if cognitive dissonance began to manifest at age 2 (Wiesmann et al., 2022) and persists into old age, choice-induced preferences in toddlers and attitude-discrepant behaviour in the elderly account for the differences between these two states (Cooper and Feldman, 2019). Thus, adolescence—a time of great psychological and physical change—became a crucial period for the study of cognitive dissonance. According to Fazakas-DeHoog et al. (2017), there is evidence that psychological discomforts and these tendencies are more common in young people, especially suicide, says Carl Fleisher, MD, who specializes in adolescent and child psychiatry at UCLA Health and is now at Boston Child Study Center in Los Angeles. In addition, Dr. Fleisher stated that "teens and young adults have had rising rates of suicide compared to 10 or 15 years ago" (Cohen, 2022). Additionally, a worldwide survey of school-aged children (ages 13 to 17) revealed that the prevalence of suicidal ideation was 16.2% (15.6, 16.7) for males and 12.2% (11.7–12.7) for females, respectively, while the percentage for suicidal ideation with a specific plan was 8.3% (95% CI; 7.9–8.7) for females and 5.8% (95% CI; 5.5–6.1) for males (McKinnon et al., 2016). According to published research, 75% of all teenage suicides occur in low- and middle-income countries (LMIC) (McKinnon et al., 2016; Uddin et al., 2019). It became crucial to research adolescent's cognitive dissonance as a result. Adolescence is an important phase with both psychological and physical changes that occur due to continuous development. This stage is marked by the establishment of new attitudes, values, and interests. It is a transitional phase from childhood to adulthood a lot of confusion among teenagers is common leading to conflict with people around them (Hurlock, 1978; Morgan et al., 2001). Regarding this, Pathak et al. (2011), stated the prevalence of behavioural and emotional problems in adolescents that were found to be 30%, with girls exceeding boys. Internalizing syndrome was the most common (28.6%) psychiatric problem. Pathak also stressed the fact that an alarming number of adolescents suffer from emotional and behavioural problems which have their roots in the family environment. These behavioural disorders are linked to stress, anxiety, criminality, aggression, fear, and dissonance—all of which are prevalent problems in today's society. Everybody encounters stress at some point in their lives. Nonetheless, a wide range of symptoms and illnesses that have an impact on our health might arise as a result of various types of dissonance. Dissonance alleviation has to do with how well

or poorly our efforts work out. Thus, dissonance is defined as a state of poor bodily and mental health brought on by unpleasant circumstances outside our control.

The concept of cognitive dissonance emerged in academia in 1957 (Lewin, 1957), therefore, the role of the student's support system becomes the utmost priority. Along with this as parents are the first teachers for a child it also becomes important to understand their impact on cognitive dissonance. Thus, the study aims to understand and find the relationship between the student support system and cognitive dissonance, and on the other hand, the study aims to understand the impact between parent qualification and cognitive dissonance.

OPERATIONAL DEFINITIONS

1. Adolescent Learners

Adolescent learners in this study refer to students studying in 9th grade at private schools affiliated with P.S.E.B.

2. Cognitive Dissonance

In the present study, Cognitive Dissonance is defined as the dissonant relationship between two cognitions when one does not logically follow from the other (Bhagwat, 1982).

3. Student Support Systems

The student support system is operationally confined to the system of institutional support services such as teachers, technology, school administration, guidance counselling, and infrastructure.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

“EFFECT OF STUDENT SUPPORT SYSTEM ON MANAGEMENT OF COGNITIVE DISSONANCE AMONG 9TH GRADE ADOLESCENT LEARNERS”

DELIMITATION OF THE STUDY

The study was delimited to the following:

1. The study was delimited to private schools affiliated with PSEB.
2. To study was delimited to 9th-grade adolescent learners of private schools affiliated to PSEB from Amritsar district of Punjab state only.
3. The study was delimited to ten private schools only.
4. The study was delimited to 200 adolescent learners only.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To construct and develop a questionnaire on the student support system.
2. To find the value of Cognitive Dissonance among 9th-grade learners with respect to boys and girls.
3. To study the relationship between Cognitive Dissonance and support system among 9th grade learners with respect to boys and girls.
4. To study the impact of parental qualification on the Cognitive Dissonance of students.

HYPOTHESIS OF THE STUDY

1. There is no significant relationship in the Cognitive Dissonance and student support system of 9th grade adolescent boys and girls.

1.10 RESEARCH QUESTION

1. What is the status of Cognitive Dissonance among 9th-grade adolescent learners with respect to boys and girls?
2. What is the impact of parental qualification on the Cognitive Dissonance of the students?

POPULATION

The entire group from which the sample is drawn is known as the population, which refers to the entire group of individuals, objects, or events that possess specific characteristics and are of interest to the researcher. A population is a well-defined group of individuals. For the present study, IX grade students of PSEB schools of Amritsar district is the population of the study.

SAMPLING TECHNIQUE

In the present study, a random sampling technique has been employed for the students of the sample.

SAMPLE

A sample of 200 students has been taken from 10 private schools of Amritsar district. Out of these 100 boys and 100 girls have been taken. All the 200, 9th-grade students selected from 10 private affiliated PSEB schools were taken as a sample for the present study.

VARIABLES OF THE STUDY

The following are the variables taken under the study:

1. **INDEPENDENT VARIABLE:** Student Support System
2. **DEPENDENT VARIABLE:** Cognitive Dissonance
3. **CATEGORIAL VARIABLE:** Parent qualification

METHOD AND PROCEDURE OF THE STUDY

A descriptive study is selected for conducting the present research whereby survey as a technique was adopted by following the procedure mentioned below:

TOOLS USED:

The following are the tools used for gathering data in the present study:

1. **EXPERIMENT ON COGNITIVE DISSONANCE (Bhagwat, 1982):** This tool is prepared by Bhagwat (1982), to check cognitive dissonance. This tool has three parts with each part containing 16 questions. Parts 1 and 2 measure cognitive dissonance among students and Part 3 helps to decrease dissonance among students. Each question has two boxes with options to agree/disagree. The validity of a tool or many measuring depends upon the fidelity with which it measures what it tends to measure. A test is valid if it serves the purpose. This test has construct and content validity.
2. **QUESTIONNAIRE FOR STUDENT'S SUPPORT SYSTEM CONSTRUCTED BY INVESTIGATOR:** To understand the role of the Student Support System in cognitive dissonance, a questionnaire for the Student Support System was developed to get responses from students regarding:
 - (i) Student Support System provided by institutions.
 - (ii) Extent to which they use these facilities.
 - (iii) Problems of Student Support System.

For the development of the tool (i.e., questionnaire for Student Support System) guidelines regarding infrastructure from; Samagra Shiksha, RMSA, PSEB, and CBSE were considered, and compiled information was analyzed to frame questions. Initially, the questionnaire was sent for expert opinion and based on suggestions after the removal of certain items: In the questionnaire I (i.e., Awareness of students on student support system) 35 questions were retained. In questionnaire II (i.e., Extent of use of Student Support System) 1 questions were retained, and finally for questionnaire III (i.e., Problems of Student Support System) 41 questions were retained.

The items were developed in statement form Yes-No (questionnaire I); Three-point Likert scale (questionnaire II); and Five-point Likert scale (questionnaire III). After the final selection of items, the validity of the questionnaire was ensured. For this tool, Content and Face validity has been established. For Content and Face validity, the constructed items were sent to the experts in the field. Every item was analyzed and thoroughly reviewed regarding;

Precision, clarity, accuracy, relevance of items, and inclusion of essential elements. And, it was validated that the items represent what it aims to measure.

SCORING OF THE QUESTIONNAIRE ON STUDENT SUPPORT SYSTEM

The questionnaire for the Student Support System is divided into 3 sections.

(1) Section I - Yes / No type Likert scale is used. For 'yes' 1 score is given and for 'No' 0 score is given.

Table 1: Scoring For 2-Point Likert Scale

Answer	Yes	No
Statement	1	0

Section II - This is a three-point Likert scale where '0' is given to statements having 'never' as response '1' mark is given to the items having 'sometimes' as response and '2' marks is given to items having 'always' as response.

Table 2: Scoring For 3-Point Likert Scale

Answer	Always	Sometimes	Never
Statement	2	1	0

Section - III includes a five-point Likert scale where '1' score is given to 'Strongly Disagree' as a response, 'a 2' score is given to 'Disagree' as a response, '3' score is given to 'Undecided' as a response, '4' score is given to 'Agree' as response and '5' score is given to 'Strongly' as response.

Table 3: Scoring For 5-Point Likert Scale

Answer	Strongly agree	Agree	Undecided	Disagree	Strongly disagree
Statement	5	4	3	2	1

STATISTICAL TECHNIQUE USED

The following statistical technique was used to analyze the obtained data:

Descriptive Statistics: Mean and standard deviation have been computed to understand the nature of data.

The value of the Coefficient correlation ‘r’ was to find the relationship between cognitive dissonance and the student support system; the percentage was also calculated to understand the impact of parental qualification on cognitive dissonance.

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

NULL HYPOTHESIS (H₀) 1: THERE IS NO SIGNIFICANT RELATIONSHIP IN THE COGNITIVE DISSONANCE AND STUDENT SUPPORT SYSTEM OF 9TH GRADE ADOLESCENT BOYS AND GIRLS

This null hypothesis was framed to ascertain that there is no significant relationship in the cognitive dissonance and student support system of 9th grade adolescent boys and girls.

To test this hypothesis, correlation was applied to determine relationship in the cognitive dissonance among 9th grade adolescent boys and girls. The result of this analysis is reported in the Table 4:

Table 4: Value of Coefficient Correlation

Variable	Gender	N	df	Coefficient Correlation (r)	Level of Significance
Student Support System & Cognitive Dissonance	Boys	100	98	-0.023	At 0.01 level
	Girls	100	98	-0.102	

It is depicted from the table that the correlation coefficient of student support and cognitive dissonance score was found to be -0.023 in boys and -0.102 in girls which is insignificant at a 0.01 level of significance. Thus, the hypothesis “THERE IS NO SIGNIFICANT RELATIONSHIP IN THE COGNITIVE DISSONANCE AND STUDENT SUPPORT SYSTEM OF 9TH GRADE ADOLESCENT BOYS AND GIRLS” is rejected. It is also analyzed that, there is a difference in the values of the correlation-coefficient of boys and girls as well that further depicts that girls have a perfect negative correlation i.e., more than boys for cognitive dissonance and student support system.

RESEARCH QUESTION 1: WHAT IS THE STATUS OF COGNITIVE DISSONANCE AMONG 9TH GRADE ADOLESCENT BOYS AND GIRLS?

In order to understand, the status of cognitive dissonance among ‘9th grade adolescent boys’ and girls’, descriptive analysis was done. The following Table 5 highlights the results of the descriptive analysis:

Table 5: Descriptive Status

	Groups	N	Mean	Median	SD	SE
Total consistency	Girls	100	12.0	12.0	1.61	0.161
	Boys	100	11.7	12.0	1.83	0.183

Based on the mean value from the data it is observed that the value of consistency on the scale of the experiment of Cognitive Dissonance among girls (i.e., 12.0) is more than the boys (i.e., 11.7). Further, it is concluded that the boys have more cognitive dissonance than the girls.

RESEARCH QUESTION 2: WHAT IS THE IMPACT OF PARENTAL QUALIFICATION ON THE COGNITIVE DISSONANCE OF 9th GRADE ADOLESCENT BOYS AND GIRLS?

In order to understand the impact of parent’s qualification on the cognitive dissonance of adolescent boys and girls. For these two groups were made:

1. GROUP A: BOTH PARENTS HAVING SAME QUALIFICATION
2. GROUP B: PARENTS HAVING DIFFERENT QUALIFICATION (for this group highest qualification of any one of the parents was considered)

GROUP A: BOTH PARENTS HAVING SAME QUALIFICATION

For doing the analysis, the group was further categorized into following sub-groups:

- a) PARENTAL QUALIFICATION: LESS THAN 10TH
- b) PARENTAL QUALIFICATION: 10TH
- c) PARENTAL QUALIFICATION: 10+ 2
- d) PARENTAL QUALIFICATION: GRADUATION
- e) PARENTAL QUALIFICATION: POST- GRADUATION

ANALYSIS OF GROUP A: BOTH PARENTS HAVING SAME QUALIFICATION

For the analysis, percentage analysis is adopted as a statistical measure.

ANALYSIS OF PARENTAL QUALIFICATION: LESS THAN 10TH

Table 6: Values of Inconsistency

Level of Inconsistency	No. of the Students
4	3
5	2
6	1
7	3
8	2
9	2
10	2

Upon analysis it is found that the level of inconsistency ranges between 4-10 where 4 is the lowest value of inconsistency and 10 is the highest value of inconsistency. Further, it is observed from the data derived that, 50-57% of total change is observed from inconsistency to consistency meaning thereby that the adolescents are aware of their dissonant behaviour and they can change in a consistent direction to achieve consonance.

ANALYSIS OF PARENTAL QUALIFICATION: 10TH

Table 7: Values of Inconsistency

Level of Inconsistency	No. of the Students
0	1
1	0
2	1
3	2
4	3
5	9
6	8
7	4
8	5
9	0
10	3
11	1

Upon analysis, it is found that the level of inconsistency ranges between 0-11 where 0 is the lowest value of inconsistency and 11 is the highest value of inconsistency. Further, it is observed from the data derived that, 33-100% of total change is observed from inconsistency to consistency meaning thereby that the adolescents are aware of their dissonant behaviour and they can change in a consistent direction to achieve consonance.

Note: only one case of 100% change is observed.

ANALYSIS OF PARENTAL QUALIFICATION: 10+ 2

Table 8: Values of Inconsistency

Level of Inconsistency	No. of the Students
1	1
2	1
3	3
4	6
5	8
6	10
7	7
8	4
9	1

Upon analysis, it is found that the level of inconsistency ranges between 1-9 where 1 is the lowest value of inconsistency and 9 is the highest value of inconsistency. Further, it is observed from the data derived that, 33-100% in total change is observed from inconsistency to consistency meaning thereby that the adolescents are aware of their dissonant behaviour and they can change in a consistent direction to achieve consonance.

Note: only three cases of 100% change are observed.

ANALYSIS OF PARENTAL QUALIFICATION: GRADUATION

Table 9: Values of Inconsistency

Level of Inconsistency	No. of the Students
5	1
6	4
7	2
8	1
9	2
10	0
11	1

Upon analysis, it is found that the level of inconsistency ranges between 5-11 where 5 is the lowest value of inconsistency and 11 is the highest value of inconsistency. Further, it is observed from the data derived that, 28-88% in total change is observed from inconsistency to consistency meaning thereby that the adolescents are aware of their dissonant behaviour and they can change in a consistent direction to achieve consonance.

Note: only one case of 28% change is observed.

ANALYSIS OF PARENTAL QUALIFICATION: POST – GRADUATION

Table 10: Values of Inconsistency

Level of Inconsistency	No. of the Students
5	1
6	1
7	1
8	1

Upon analysis, it is found that the level of inconsistency ranges between 5-8 where 5 is the lowest value of inconsistency and 8 is the highest value of inconsistency. Further, it is observed from the data derived that, 43-100% of total change is observed from inconsistency to consistency meaning thereby that the adolescents are aware of their dissonant behaviour and they can change in a consistent direction to achieve consonance.

Thus, it is concluded that in the case of parents having the same qualification

GROUP B: PARENTS HAVING DIFFERENT QUALIFICATION (for this group highest qualification of any one of the parents was considered)

For doing the analysis, the group was further categorized into the following sub-groups:

- a) MISCELLANEOUS GROUP (this group includes parents with less than 10th as qualification. Following criteria is adopted to make this a group: i.e., parents with highest qualification as 9th, 8th, 5th and so on are considered)
- b) 10TH AS HIGHEST QUALIFICATION
- c) 10 +2 AS HIGHEST QUALIFICATION
- d) GRADUATION AS HIGHEST QUALIFICATION
- e) POST-GRADUATION AS HIGHEST QUALIFICATION

ANALYSIS OF PARENTAL QUALIFICATION: MISCELLANEOUS GROUP

Table 11: Values of Inconsistency

Level of Inconsistency	No. of the Students
3	3
4	2
5	2
6	0
7	1
8	0
9	1
10	1
11	3

Upon analysis, it is found that the level of inconsistency ranges between 2-9 where 2 is the lowest value of inconsistency and 9 is the highest value of inconsistency. Further, it is observed from the data derived that, 36% - 77% of total change is observed from inconsistency to consistency meaning thereby that the adolescents are aware of their dissonant behaviour and they can change in a consistent direction to achieve consonance.

Note: only one case of 77% change is observed.

ANALYSIS OF PARENTAL QUALIFICATION: 10TH AS HIGHEST QUALIFICATION

Table 12: Values of Inconsistency

Level of Inconsistency	No. of the Students
2	2
3	3
4	0
5	4
6	5
7	2
8	0
9	2

Upon analysis, it is found that the level of inconsistency ranges between 2-9 where 2 is the lowest value of inconsistency and 9 is the highest value of inconsistency. Further, it is observed from the data derived that, 33% - 100% of total change is observed from inconsistency to consistency meaning thereby that the adolescents are aware of their dissonant behaviour and they can change in a consistent direction to achieve consonance.

Note: only two cases of 100% change are observed.

ANALYSIS OF PARENTAL QUALIFICATION: 10 +2 AS HIGHEST QUALIFICATION

Table 13: Values of Inconsistency

Level of Inconsistency	No. of the Students
2	1
3	1
4	7
5	3
6	14
7	7
8	5
9	3
10	2
11	1

Upon analysis, it is found that the level of inconsistency ranges between 3-11 where 3 is the lowest value of inconsistency and 11 is the highest value of inconsistency. Further, it is observed from the data derived that, 33%-100% total change is observed from inconsistency to consistency meaning thereby that the adolescents are aware of their dissonant behaviour and they can change in a consistent direction to achieve consonance.

Note: only five cases of 100% change are observed.

ANALYSIS OF PARENTAL QUALIFICATION: GRADUATION AS HIGHEST QUALIFICATION

Table 14: Values of Inconsistency

Level of Inconsistency	No. of the Students
4	1
5	1
6	4
7	1
8	2

Upon analysis, it is found that the level of inconsistency ranges between 4-8 where 4 is the lowest value of inconsistency and 8 is the highest value of inconsistency. Further, it is observed from the data derived that, 50% - 75% of total change is observed from inconsistency to consistency meaning thereby that the adolescents are aware of their dissonant behaviour and they can change in a consistent direction to achieve consonance.

ANALYSIS OF PARENTAL QUALIFICATION: POST-GRADUATION AS HIGHEST QUALIFICATION

Table 15: Values of Inconsistency

Level of Inconsistency	No. of the Students
5	2
6	3
7	2

Upon analysis, it is found that the level of inconsistency ranges between 5-7 where 5 is the lowest value of inconsistency and 7 is the highest value of inconsistency. Further, it is observed from the data derived that, 60% - 100% in total change is observed from the inconsistency to consistency meaning thereby that the adolescents are aware of their dissonant behavior and they can change in a consistent direction to achieve consonance.

FINDINGS OF THE STUDY:

Based on the results it is concluded that:

1. There exists a significant negative correlation between the student support system and cognitive dissonance of 9th-grade adolescent boys and girls. It is also analyzed that, there is a difference in the values of correlation-coefficient of boys and girls as well that further depicts that girls have a perfect negative correlation i.e., more than boys with respect to cognitive dissonance and student support system.
2. Upon analysis it is found that girls have less cognitive dissonant behaviour than boys.
3. It is also concluded from the analysis that in group A as well as in group B level of inconsistency varies from 0-11. Further, it is observed that inconsistency of students whose parents are least qualified is more as compared to adolescents whose parents are more qualified. And even if, any adolescent will the least parental qualification has inconsistency less than others their number is minimal i.e., one to four cases in total.
4. Furthermore, when total change in inconsistency is observed from the data it is concluded that maximum students whose parents have less qualification depict total change $\geq 50\%$, and if 100% change exists that change is observed only among 2-5 cases in both the groups.
5. On the other hand, the maximum students whose parents have the highest qualification i.e., graduation or post-graduation total change in inconsistency is $\leq 50\%$ in both the groups.
6. Lastly it is concluded that adolescents with a high parental qualification in both groups are slightly more aware of their dissonant behaviour or have less cognitive dissonance and they can change in a consistent direction to achieve consonance.

CONCLUSION

The study revealed that the student support system has a negative correlation with the cognitive dissonance of IX grade learners of P.S.E.B schools, which that means, with the proper student support system, cognitive dissonance can be reduced. The study indicated that boys from these schools have higher cognitive dissonance scores than girls. And also concluded that parental qualification has an impact on cognitive dissonance. Based on this it is recommended that policymakers, administrators, and school management should focus on enhancing the student support system so that the cognitive dissonance of students can be reduced. Apart from this, policymakers and administrators should take steps to build a new education system for adults

and create awareness among parents. lastly, counselling and guiding sessions should be made available to the students regarding the occurrence of dissonance and how it can be reduced.

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